

Development of Worksheet for Students (LKPD) with Project Based Learning (PjBL) in the Material of Manipulative Basic Moves Pattern for Improving the Learning Outcomes of Fourth Grade Students

Wahyu Sholichatun¹, Soni Nopembri²

^{1,2}Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta, Yogyakarta, DIY, 55281, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The development of Project-Based Learning (PjBL) Student Worksheets (LKPD) on basic manipulative moves material to improve learning outcomes for fourth grade students of elementary school aims to facilitate students in the Physical Education (PE) learning process on basic manipulative movement material. The development of these LKPDs takes the form of printed teaching materials in book form. This research was a research and development (R&D) study following the 4D development model with the stages of Define, Design, Develop, and Disseminate. The PjBL-based LKPDs were declared valid and feasible by experts in their fields. Three validators were employed as material experts and one validator was employed as a media expert. The trial was conducted at SDN Sewukan 1 (Sewukan 1 Elementary School), Dukun District. The data analysis involved in comparing the assessment results for each aspect with the expected feasibility level, which was then elaborated in percentages. This research analyzed student learning outcomes by using the LKPDs. The development results are: (1) the developed product has gone through various development stages such as the format selection process, product creation, validation stage by material experts, media experts, and student learning outcomes in using the product (LKPD) based on (PjBL) basic manipulative movement material to improve the learning outcomes of fourth grade students of elementary school, (2) the product created is included in the category of suitable for use in the learning process, (3) student learning outcomes can be improved after using Student Worksheets (LKPD) based on Project Based Learning (PjBL) in the basic manipulative movement material to improve the learning outcomes of fourth grade students of elementary school.

KEYWORDS: LKPD, PjBL Learning, Manipulative Movement, and Learning Outcomes

I. INTRODUCTION

The learning process under the Merdeka Curriculum requires teachers to play a role not only as knowledge providers but also as mentors and facilitators. Teachers must be able to design contextual and engaging lessons that encourage students to be active and independent in the learning process. One approach that can facilitate children's active learning and help them more easily understand the material presented is by providing effective instructional materials, such as Student Worksheets (LKPD). LKPDs serve as guides for learning activities that allow students to explore the material independently or collaboratively (Prastowo, 2015).

The results of observations and interviews conducted by the researcher at elementary schools in Dukun Subdistrict indicate that teachers have not yet optimally utilized worksheets as instructional materials in their teaching practices. In the current learning process, teachers tend to use commercially available worksheets, which often contain excessive text, less engaging illustrations, and insufficiently detailed task instructions. As a result, students become easily bored, demonstrate low levels of participation, and show limited creativity in problem solving.

Student engagement is a key factor in the success of the learning process, particularly in fostering active participation and meaningful learning experiences. Learning that does not involve students actively will tend to reduce motivation and participation levels. Recent studies show that learning models and media that are less interactive can negatively impact students' engagement and problem-solving skills (Asmara Andik., & Ma, 2024).

Given these issues, it is necessary to develop Student Worksheets (LKPD) that can actively engage students in the learning process. One effective approach to address students' boredom and lack of independence is the implementation of Project Based

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Learning (PjBL). This model emphasizes learning through real world projects and collaborative activities that encourage students to actively construct their knowledge. Research indicates that Project Based Learning significantly improves student engagement when learning is contextual and connected to real-life situations (Yunjeong. et al., 2024).

In addition, Project Based Learning has been proven to increase students' motivation, creativity, and learning outcomes. The use of projects allows students to explore ideas, collaborate with peers, and develop problem solving skills more effectively. Furthermore, the integration of project based activities has also been shown to improve students' attitudes and engagement in learning environments aligned with the Merdeka Curriculum (Widiastuti Anik & Fahmi, 2024).

In the context of Physical Education, Sports, and Health (PJOK), the implementation of PjBL is highly relevant because it supports not only psychomotor development but also cognitive and affective domains. Through project based activities, students are encouraged to participate actively, collaborate, and develop higher-order thinking skills, which are essential competencies in 21st century learning.

Physical Education, Sports, and Health (PJOK) in elementary schools covers various learning materials, one of which is fundamental movement skills. These fundamental movements are generally classified into three categories: locomotor, nonlocomotor, and manipulative movements. In the context of this study, the researcher focuses on manipulative fundamental movement skills, as they are aligned with the learning outcomes and objectives for Phase B in elementary education.

However, the current learning process in schools has not been able to optimally engage students in mastering both conceptual understanding and practical skills related to manipulative movements. This limitation significantly affects students' learning outcomes, as many students still do not achieve the Minimum Mastery Criteria (KKM), which is set at 75. Low student engagement and lack of interactive learning media are among the key factors contributing to this issue. Previous studies indicate that conventional teaching approaches in PJOK tend to limit students' active participation and reduce learning effectiveness (Widodo, 2022).

In addition, the use of appropriate instructional materials, such as LKPD, plays an important role in improving students' engagement and learning outcomes. Well-designed LKPD can guide students to actively participate in learning activities, explore concepts independently, and collaborate with peers (Sari, 2023). Based on these problems, this study aims to develop a ProjectBased Learning (PjBL) based LKPD on manipulative fundamental movement skills for fourth grade elementary school students. This development is expected to enhance students' learning activeness, increase their learning interest, and improve learning outcomes through meaningful and contextual learning experiences.

II. METHOD

The Disseminate stage is the final phase in the 4D development model, which aims to implement and distribute the revised product so that it can be used more broadly in educational settings. At this stage, the developed worksheets are introduced to a wider audience, such as teachers and students in different schools, to ensure their applicability and effectiveness in real learning environments.

The dissemination stage includes several important activities, namely validation testing, packaging, and diffusion. Validation testing is conducted to ensure that the final product meets quality standards in terms of content, design, and usability. Packaging refers to the process of preparing the product in a form that is ready to be used or distributed, such as printed or digital formats. Meanwhile, diffusion involves the process of spreading and implementing the product to a broader target audience.

The dissemination of well-developed instructional materials plays a crucial role in improving the quality of teaching and learning processes. Research shows that the distribution of validated and practical LKPD can support teachers in implementing more interactive and student centered learning (Prasetyo Andi, A & Lestari Dian, 2022). In addition, effective dissemination ensures that educational innovations can be adopted widely and sustainably across different educational contexts (Wahyuni Sri et al., 2023).

Furthermore, the use of dissemination strategies such as training, workshops, and digital sharing platforms has been proven to increase teachers' understanding and readiness in applying newly developed learning tools (Hidayah Nur, 2021). Therefore, the Disseminate stage is not only about distributing products but also ensuring their successful adoption and implementation in improving learning quality.

The data collection techniques used in this study included interviews, observations, product quality assessment, student response questionnaires, as well as pretest and posttest to measure students' learning outcomes. These techniques were employed to obtain comprehensive data related to the effectiveness and feasibility of the developed Project Based Learning (PjBL) based worksheets on manipulative fundamental movement skills.

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The collected data were analyzed using both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Qualitative data analysis was based on feedback, suggestions, and validation results provided by material experts, media experts, and students' responses toward the developed LKPD. This analysis aimed to improve the quality and suitability of the product in accordance with the learning objectives.

Meanwhile, quantitative data analysis was used to process numerical data obtained from expert validation questionnaires, student response questionnaires, and pretest posttest results. The validation instruments used a Likert scale with five categories: 1 = very poor/very inappropriate, 2 = poor/inappropriate, 3 = fair/moderately appropriate, 4 = good/appropriate, and 5 = very good/very appropriate.

The scores obtained from material and media expert validations were averaged for each aspect to determine the feasibility level of the PjBL based LKPD. Furthermore, the mean scores were converted into percentages and interpreted using predetermined feasibility criteria. This process allows researchers to objectively evaluate whether the developed worksheets meet the standards of validity, practicality, and effectiveness.

The use of mixed data analysis techniques in educational research is essential to ensure comprehensive evaluation, combining descriptive qualitative insights with statistical quantitative evidence. In addition, the application of Likert scale based validation has been widely used in instructional material development to measure product feasibility and user responses. Recent studies also indicate that combining expert validation and pretest posttest analysis provides strong evidence of the effectiveness of developed learning materials (Haryanto et al., 2022). Next, the average of each aspect is calculated and expressed as a percentage, then converted into a rating score as follows:

Table 1. Assessment Criteria for the Feasibility Level of Local Government Financial Reports Based on Achievement Percentage

Achievement Percentage (%)	Criteria
81% - 100%	Highly Valid/Feasible
61%-80%	Valid/Feasible
41%-60%	Moderately Valid/Feasible
21%-40%	Invalid/Unfeasible
20%	Highly Invalid/Unfeasible

An analysis of students' responses to the PjBL-based worksheets revealed four response categories (1–4), where 1 = very poor/very uninteresting, 2 = poor/uninteresting, 3 = good/interesting, and 4 = very good/very interesting (Anggara D, p. 86). The results of the student response questionnaire were analyzed and converted to determine the appeal of the PjBL-based worksheets on basic manipulative movement patterns. The analysis results were converted into assessment scores, as follows:

Table 2. Conversion of Achievement Percentage to Attractiveness Criteria

Achievement Percentage	Attractiveness Criteria
75% - 100%	Very Attractive
50% - 74%	Attractive
25% - 49%	Less Attractive
24%	Unattractive

Student learning outcomes were analyzed using pretest and posttest questions. The results were analyzed by calculating the average score of all students, which was then converted into a percentage to assess student learning achievement, with a minimum passing score of 75. The percentage of student achievement was compared with the product's effectiveness rate, as follows:

Table 3. Criteria for the Effectiveness of Worksheets Based on Student Learning Achievement

Number of students above the passing score	Rating
81% - 100%	Very Effective
61% - 80%	Effective
41% - 60%	Less Effective

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21% - 40%	Ineffective
0% - 20%	Very Ineffective

To observe improvements in students' learning outcomes before and after using PjBL-based worksheets on basic manipulative movements for fourth-grade elementary school students, this must be demonstrated with valid data using a paired-sample t-test. Data analysis using this paired-sample t-test is not only intended to observe improvements in students' learning outcomes but also to determine the effectiveness of the method. The paired-sample t-test yields the following data decisions: H_0 is accepted if the significance value is >0.05 ; if the significance value is <0.05 , H_0 is rejected. H_a is accepted if the significance value is <0.05 ; if the significance value is >0.05 , H_a is rejected.

III. RESEARCH RESULT

1. Define

Interview and observation results indicate that teachers have not yet utilized the Student Worksheet (LKPD) optimally. Learning remains teacher centered, and teachers still use lecture and command methods. Student learning outcomes have not yet reached the Minimum Competency (KKM) as several students still scored below it. Therefore, the development of a PjBL based Student Worksheet (LKPD) on basic manipulative movement material is needed to improve the learning outcomes of fourth grade elementary school students.

2. Design

Based on the analysis results from the previous stage, the researcher then drafted a PjBL based Student Worksheet. The format includes a title, user instructions, learning objectives, learning activities, evaluation, and a bibliography.

3. Development

In the development stage, the researcher validated the worksheet with material and media experts before conducting field trials. Input and direction from the validation of material and media experts, namely, a material expert with one lecturer validator and two physical education teacher validators, provided input on the student worksheet (LKPD) product created by the researcher. The input from the first material expert was for slightly more detail and additional learning media to help students gain insight into the material. The second material expert's input was for learning activities to modify baseball bats and baseballs. The initial design utilized only plastic waste. Later, input was given to use used materials or materials found around the school environment, such as tree branches, used building wood, and plastic waste. Meanwhile, the media validation stated "don't use too many types of writing," therefore the author revised the writing style to match the existing Comic Sans Ms. format.

The product trial was conducted at SDN Sewukan 1, Dukun District, Magelang Regency, with 21 students. This product trial used an experimental technique, with students given a Student Worksheet (LKPD) PjBL (PjBL) on basic manipulative movement. The product trial aims to see the attractiveness or feasibility of the LKPD by having children fill out a questionnaire on student responses to the PjBL based LKPD used.

4. Dissemination

The researcher obtained the final draft of the worksheet, which was then implemented in a real classroom (validation testing). The worksheet was printed in booklets and distributed to students. During this stage, the researcher also administered pretests and posttests to assess student learning outcomes. To determine the effectiveness of the PjBL-based worksheet development for manipulative basic movement material in improving learning outcomes for fourth-grade elementary school students, data were analyzed using a paired sample t-test. With a significance value (2-tailed) of <0.001 or a significance value of <0.005 , H_0 was rejected and H_a was accepted. These results indicate that there is a difference in learning outcomes using the PjBL-based worksheet for manipulative basic movement material.

IV. DISCUSSION

1. Feasibility of PjBL-Based LKPD to Improve Students' Learning Outcomes on Basic Manipulative Movement Patterns for Fourth Grade Elementary School Students

a. Validation by Material Experts

The feasibility of the developed Project Based Learning (PjBL) based LKPD was evaluated through material expert validation to determine its appropriateness for improving students' learning outcomes, particularly in the topic of basic manipulative movement patterns for fourth grade elementary school students. The results of the validation are presented in Table 4 below.

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Table 4. Percentage Results of Material Expert Validation for Each Aspect

No	Assessment Aspect	Percentage (%)	Category
1	Didactic	95%	Very Valid/Feasible
2	Constructive	97%	Very Valid/Feasible
3	Technical	97%	Very Valid/Feasible
4	Content Quality	95%	Very Valid/Feasible
5	PjBL Based	91%	Very Valid/Feasible
	Average	95%	Very Valid/Feasible

Based on Table 4, it can be observed that all assessed aspects achieved scores within the “very valid/feasible” category. The didactic aspect obtained a score of 95%, indicating that the learning objectives and instructional strategies are well aligned with students’ needs. The constructive aspect reached 97%, showing that the structure and organization of the worksheets are systematically designed. Similarly, the technical aspect scored 97%, reflecting the clarity and quality of the presentation.

Furthermore, the content quality aspect achieved 95%, which indicates that the material is accurate, relevant, and appropriate for fourth-grade elementary school students. The PjBL based aspect obtained a score of 91%, demonstrating that the integration of Project-Based Learning principles has been effectively implemented in the worksheets.

The overall average score of 95% confirms that the developed LKPD meets a very high level of validity. This suggests that the worksheets are highly feasible to be used in the learning process. In addition, the high validation results indicate that the developed product is capable of supporting meaningful, student centered learning and has strong potential to improve students’ learning outcomes, especially in mastering basic manipulative movement skills.

b. Media Expert Validation

The feasibility of the developed Project Based Learning (PjBL)-based LKPD was also evaluated through media expert validation to assess its quality in terms of visual design, readability, and usability in the learning process. The results of the validation are presented in Table 5 below.

Table 5. Percentage Results of Media Expert Validation for Each Aspect

No	Assessment Aspect	Percentage (%)	Category
1	Visual Appearance	100%	Very Valid/Feasible
2	Font and Typography	93%	Very Valid/Feasible
3	Content Feasibility	97%	Very Valid/Feasible
4	Usefulness	100%	Very Valid/Feasible
	Average	97.5%	Very Valid/Feasible

Based on Table 5, all aspects evaluated by the media expert fall into the “very valid/feasible” category. The visual appearance aspect achieved a perfect score of 100%, indicating that the design of the worksheets is highly attractive and appropriate for elementary school students. The font and typography aspect obtained a score of 93%, showing that the text is readable and well organized, although minor improvements may still be possible.

Furthermore, the content feasibility aspect reached 97%, reflecting that the material is clearly presented and well integrated into the media design. The usefulness aspect also obtained a perfect score of 100%, indicating that the developed LKPD is highly beneficial in supporting the learning process.

The overall average score of 97.5% indicates that the media quality of the developed PjBL based LKPD is at an excellent level of validity. These findings demonstrate that the worksheets are visually appealing, easy to use, and effective as instructional media. Therefore, the LKPD is highly feasible to be implemented in the learning process to enhance students’ learning outcomes, particularly in basic manipulative movement skills for fourth-grade elementary school students.

2. Student Responses to PjBL Based LKPD

Student responses were collected to evaluate the attractiveness of the developed Project-Based Learning (PjBL) based LKPD in improving students’ learning outcomes on basic manipulative movement patterns for fourth-grade elementary school students. The responses were obtained at the end of the learning process to assess students’ perceptions after using the worksheets during the implementation. The results are presented in Table 6 below.

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Table 6. Percentage of Student Responses for Each Aspect

No	Assessment Aspect	Percentage (%)	Category
1	Cover Design	100%	Very Attractive
2	Content Design	99%	Very Attractive
	Average	99.5%	Very Attractive

Based on Table 6, the results show that students' responses to the PjBL-based LKPD fall into the "very attractive" category across all assessed aspects. The cover design aspect achieved a perfect score of 100%, indicating that the visual appearance of the worksheets is highly engaging and appealing to students. Meanwhile, the content design aspect obtained a score of 99%, demonstrating that the layout, structure, and presentation of the material are also very attractive and easy to understand.

The overall average score of 99.5% indicates that the developed LKPD has an excellent level of attractiveness. These findings suggest that the integration of Project Based Learning (PjBL) elements, combined with an appealing visual design, successfully enhances students' interest and engagement during the learning process.

Furthermore, the high level of student satisfaction reflects that the worksheets not only support learning activities but also create a positive and enjoyable learning experience. Therefore, it can be concluded that the PjBL based LKPD is highly attractive and suitable for use in improving students' learning outcomes, particularly in basic manipulative movement skills for fourthgrade elementary school students.

3. Students' Learning Outcomes of PjBL Based LKPD

The effectiveness of the developed Project-Based Learning (PjBL) based LKPD was evaluated through students' learning outcomes using pretest and posttest scores. The results indicate an improvement in students' scores after the implementation of the worksheets. The summary of the results is presented in Table 7 below.

Table 7. Summary of Students' Learning Outcomes (Pretest and Posttest)

No	Indicator	Result
1	Number of Students	21
2	Average Pretest Score	72
3	Average Posttest Score	88
4	Highest Posttest Score	96
5	Lowest Pretest Score	48
6	Significance (Sig.)	< 0.001
	Category	Very Effective

Based on Table 7 and the graphical data, there is a noticeable improvement in students' learning outcomes after the implementation of the PjBL based LKPD. The average pretest score was 72, while the average posttest score increased to 88, indicating a substantial improvement in students' performance.

In addition, the highest posttest score reached 96, while the lowest pretest score was 48, showing that even students with lower initial performance experienced improvement after the intervention. This suggests that the developed worksheets are effective in supporting students with varying levels of ability.

Furthermore, the paired-sample t-test analysis revealed a significance value of less than 0.001 ($p < 0.001$), which indicates a statistically significant difference between pretest and posttest scores. This means that the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted.

These findings confirm that the use of PjBL based LKPD significantly improves students' learning outcomes. The integration of project-based activities encourages active participation, enhances understanding, and promotes meaningful learning experiences. Therefore, it can be concluded that the developed LKPD falls into the "very effective" category and is highly suitable for use in improving students' learning outcomes in basic manipulative movement skills for fourth-grade elementary school students.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the research and development of a PjBLbased worksheet (LKPD) to improve student learning outcomes in the basic manipulative movement patterns material for fourth grade elementary school students, the following conclusions can be drawn:

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1. A PjBL based worksheet has been developed to improve student learning outcomes in the basic manipulative movement patterns material for fourth-grade elementary school students. This worksheet is also structured with attractive images, diverse learning activities, and illustrations that are easy for students to understand.
2. The feasibility of the PjBL based worksheet, validated by material experts, was 95%, media experts 98%, and student responses 99%. All results fall into the "Very Valid" and "Very Interesting" categories.
3. Tests of effectiveness and improvement in student learning outcomes through pretests and posttests showed an increase in learning outcomes from 33% to 86%, which falls into the "Very Effective" category. Statistical tests showed that the calculated r value was greater than the table r value ($9.208 > 2.0$) and a significance value of $0.0001 < 0.005$, indicating a significant effect on improving student learning outcomes after using the PjBL based Student Worksheet.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the conclusions above, the researcher proposes the following:

1. Further development can be carried out by implementing and evaluating the effectiveness of the PjBL based Student Worksheet product to improve student learning outcomes in the basic manipulative movement pattern material for fourth grade elementary school students.
2. Future research can develop the Student Worksheet with other models, increasing the number of students and classes.

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